

INTERPHASE DEGRADATION IN GFRP UNDER ACIDIC CONDITION

Machiko MIZOGUCHI*, Hiroyuki HAMADA*

Lanhong XU**, Lawrence T. DRZAL**

**Kyoto Institute of Technology, Sakyo, Kyoto, JAPAN*

*** Michigan State University, East Lansing, USA*

SUMMARY: In order to study on the degradation of GFRP under acid condition, it is very important to understand the interphase degradation behavior under acidic condition. Under acidic condition, the acid stress corrosion which is caused by the degradation of E glass fiber occurs, and C or ECR type glass fiber have been used in stead of the E glass fiber. In the case that the C or ECR glass fiber is used, the interphase degradation which is not well understood, should be focused. In this paper, the effect of interphase properties on fracture behavior and interphase properties under acidic condition were evaluated and the effect of the interphase degradation on the degradation and life of GFRP were discussed. The interphase properties affects the fracture behavior under acidic condition and the specimen in which lower concentration of silane coupling agent was used showed interface damage more severely. The degradation of mechanical properties were also affected by the interphase conditions. The result of micro indentation test of C glass fiber reinforced plastics suggests that the interfacial shear strength decreased in terms of the acid immersion time and drastically decreased in short period less than 7 days. The degradation mechanism of GFRP under acidic condition could be clarified.

KEYWORDS:GFRP, Degradation, Interphase, C glass fiber

INTRODUCTION

It has been recognized that the interface plays an important role in composite materials. Stress, vibration, heat should be transmitted through the interface between matrix and reinforcement. In order to improve the mechanical properties of composite materials, the improvement of the interface adhesion is the most effective. Therefore, various surface treatments have been developed. For example, silane coupling agent, which is the most popular, has been mainly used in GFRP. The role of the surface treatment is not only the improvement of interfacial adhesion but also to improve the handling and the protection of the reinforcements during fabrication.

By using glass fibers with surface treatments, the intermediate phase is created during fabrication because of the diffusion of the surface treatment including physisorbed silanes. The phase consists of the matrix resin and the surface treatment, and has different mechanical properties from the matrix resin. Therefore, instead of "interface", the term "interphase" term, that should have three-dimensional volume, has become popular.

Unless it has been also recognized that the interphase structure affects the degradation behavior in GFRP exposed to severe environments, the details have not been well understood. In particular interphase degradation behavior is not clarified. Therefore in this study, interphase degradation behavior in glass woven fabric reinforced vinylester composites under acidic condition was investigated, and effect of interphase condition on its degradation behavior was discussed.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL

The thermoset resin used in this study was a bisphenol A type vinylester resin (R806; Showa high polymer Co. Ltd., Japan) containing 43wt% of styrene monomer. The catalyst used was 0.7 phr methylethylketoneperoxide promoted by 0.3 phr cobalt naphthenate solution. The post cure was performed at 80°C for 3 hours and at 150°C for 2 hours. The E-glass fiber plain woven fabric(Nittobo, Japan) with the strand consisting of 400 glass filaments in 9µm diameter was used as

reinforcement. Surface treatment was performed with methacryloxypropyltrimethoxysilane (A-174: Nippon). The aqueous solutions of the MPS were acidified, and the specimens were dipped into the MPS aqueous solutions. They were immersed at 110°C for 10min. The MPS concentrations used were referred to as MPS0.01, MPS0.4, and MPS1.0. The glass fiber plain woven fabric (Mie textile, Japan) was also used for the reinforcement. The specimens were immersed in 5wt% HNO₃. Observation of fracture aspects, weight measurement, and weight loss (MI) were performed after the immersion. Fiber indentation test was also performed on the composites after the immersions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 shows the results of weight measurement, and weight loss (MI) were presented. M_a , M_g , and M_i as a function of immersion time for MPS0.01, MPS0.4, and MPS1.0 are shown in Fig. 1. M_a and M_g coming off from the specimen surface were found to be higher in MPS0.01. MPS0.01 showed larger M_g as well as larger M_i in comparison with MPS0.4 and MPS1.0. The difference in M_g among MPS0.01, MPS0.4, and MPS1.0 is shown in Fig. 1. One is the difference in fracture aspects. Debondings were observed around each filament in MPS0.4 and MPS1.0. The difference in the fracture aspects among MPS0.01, MPS0.4, and MPS1.0 is shown in Fig. 2. MPS0.01 had poor adhesion, and MPS0.4 and MPS1.0 had good adhesion when they were immersed in acidic solution. In addition, the swelling and shrinkage ratios of the glass fiber and matrix were not very much. Therefore, these differences in fracture aspects are due to the interfacial adhesion. When the interfacial adhesion remains strong even after immersion, the interfacial adhesion could not withstand the stress of the matrix. The other point of view is the interphase structures. The bonding via silane coupling agent, whereas the matrix has a cross-linked structure. Therefore, the cross-link density is high in the matrix. The cross-linked polymer is affected by the cross-linking agent. Hence, the high cross-linking density in MPS0.4 and MPS1.0 leads to the high diffusion in MPS0.4 and MPS1.0.

Fig.1 Weight change as a function of immersion time. Upper; Apparent weight gain, Middle; Net weight gain, Bottom; Weight loss

Fig.2 Fracture aspects observed by SEM after 7 days immersion.

Fig.3 Retention of flexural properties as a function of immersion time. Upper; Flexural modulus, Bottomr; Flexural strength.

Fig. 3 shows the retention of flexural properties as a function of immersion time. Both flexural modulus and strength decreased in the case of MPS0.01, unless MPS0.4 and MPS1.0 showed almost constant values. It is clearly understood that the interfacial fracture and diffusion of the solution into interphase led to the degradation of the mechanical properties which was caused by degradation of glass fiber by acid penetrating through interphase.

Hence the interphase structure and interfacial adhesion strongly affect the degradation of mechanical properties. It could be inferred that the good interfacial adhesion and dense cross link structure in interphase showed higher resistance to degradation under acidic conditions. In other words, in order to design the composite materials with higher corrosion resistance, the interphase structure must be considered, and dense cross link structure and high interfacial adhesion should be generated.

Although the interphase properties has been discussed above, these degradation behaviors are also related to and the degradation of E glass fiber which is low corrosion resistance against acid. Therefore, in order to understand the degradation of interphase properties themselves, C glass fiber, which is high resistance against acid, was used to evaluate interfacial shear strength. Fiber indentation test (ITS) was carried out. By ITS, the interfacial shear strength can be obtained from the stress at which the crack propagates around filaments, and it is not possible to use E glass fiber reinforced composite, because as shown in figure 2, the debondings and cracks occurred after acid immersion in the case of E glass fiber reinforced composites. Figure 4 shows the specimen edge of C glass fiber reinforced composites after 7 days for example. The cracks and debondings around filaments were not observed even after the acid immersion. The debondings were not observed until 60 days and specimens could be subjected to the ITS. Figure 5 shows the interfacial shear strength as a function of

Figure 4. Relationship between interfacial shear strength and immersion time.

immersion time of C glass fiber reinforced composites. The interfacial shear strength decreased approximately 40% in 7 days and showed constant values until 60 days. While cracks were not observed in the specimen, it is apparent that the interfacial properties affected by the acid immersion. In the case of E glass fiber reinforced composites, the interfacial properties definitely affected, but the effect of degradation of glass fiber should be very large. In other words, the phenomena described above are the characteristic patterns of E glass fiber reinforced composites.

CONCLUSIONS

The interphase degradation behavior under acidic condition in glass woven fabric reinforced vinylester composite was investigated. In the case of E glass fiber reinforced composites, the interphase the degradation of intephase properties and glass fiber occurred and it led to the degradation of mechanical properties. It was suggested that the interfacial adhesion and cross link structure in interphase affect the corrosion resistance performance. In the case of C glass fiber reinforced composite, as the glass fiber did not corrode, only the degradation of interfacial property could be understood. The interfacial shear strength decreased in short period (7 days) even the debondings did not appeared around the filaments until 60 days.